

FABRICATION AND APPLICATIONS OF MULTI-FUNCTIONAL NANOCOMPOSITES FILLED WITH CARBON BASED NANOMATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon based nanomaterials (CNT, graphene) have been received intensive attention as advanced nano-fillers to overcome the limitations of traditional composite materials because of their outstanding mechanical, electrical and thermal properties. The important issues of carbon nanomaterials filled nanocomposites are homogeneous dispersion of carbon nanomaterials in matrices and control of interfacial characteristics between fillers and matrices.

In this study, fabrication processes and characterizations of multi-functional nanocomposites filled with carbon based nanomaterials in various inorganic and organic matrices are reviewed. The technological issues are suggested to control the homogeneity of fillers and interfacial adhesive behavior between carbon based nanomaterials and matrices based on microstructural characterization. The results on the characterization of structural and functional properties of the nanocomposites are reviewed to understand possible application areas as multi-functional materials.

The metal matrix nanocomposites filled with carbon based nanomaterials, such as CNT/Cu, CNT/Ni, CNT/Al, Graphene/Cu, and Graphene/Mg, are suggested as advanced structural materials due to their outstanding yield strength, modulus and wear resistance. The ceramic matrix nanocomposites filled with carbon based nanomaterial, such as CNT/Al₂O₃, Graphene/Al₂O₃ and Graphene/Si₃N₄, show significantly enhanced mechanical properties including hardness, strength and fracture toughness. The polymer matrix nanocomposites filled with carbon based nanomaterials, such as CNT/Epoxy, CNT/PE, CNT/PMMA, CNT/PPV, Graphene/Epoxy, Graphene/PU, Graphene/PS and Graphene/PEDOT:PSS show wide scope functional properties for possible applications as lightweight toughened plastics, electrodes for supercapacitors & Li ion batteries, stretchable conductors and organic photovoltaic materials.

It is expected that the nanocomposites filled with carbon based nanomaterials will grow as emerging advanced multi-functional materials to replace the traditional materials or components for various upcoming applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, carbon based nanomaterials including carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphenes have received a lot of attention as important composite materials for structural and functional applications due to their outstanding mechanical strength as well as excellent electrical and thermal conductivities [1-7]. In this review we are focusing on composite materials of carbon based nanomaterials and their application with mechanical, electrical and thermal properties by various inorganic and organic matrices such as metals, ceramics and polymers. Due to small dimensions of carbon based nanomaterials exhibiting strong Van der Waals forces, they have a tendency to agglomerate and a poor interfacial bonding between carbon based nanomaterials and matrices [8-10]. To avert these problems, functionalization techniques are used i.e. covalent and non-covalent

functionalization. Incorporation of carbon based nanomaterials into the matrix results in substantial changes in the mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of composite [9-11]. Furthermore the review also discusses the importance and use of CNTs or graphene as fillers in the matrix along with their applications.

2 CARBON BASED NANOMATERIALS/METAL NANOCOMPOSITES

The main challenges for the development of MMNCs are the attainment of homogeneous dispersion of carbonaceous reinforcing materials in the metal matrix, the formation of strong interfacial bonding and the retention of structural stability of carbon based nanomaterials. Hence, many researchers have attempted to fabricate carbon based nanomaterials reinforced metal/ceramic nanocomposites by means of traditional powder metallurgy processes [12-14], which consist of carbon based nanomaterials-mixed matrix powders followed by sintering or hot pressing. However, most attempts have failed to fabricate carbon based nanomaterials/metal nanocomposites due to the agglomeration of carbon based nanomaterials. In order to overcome the poor dispersion, therefore, carbon based nanomaterials-reinforced metal nanocomposites were fabricated by the molecular-level mixing process [15]. Eventually, many kinds of carbon based nanomaterials/metal nanocomposites were developed and they showed excellent mechanical properties. By this process, the chemical bonding between the CNTs and the metal matrix ions provides homogeneous distribution of CNTs as well as high interfacial strength between CNT and metal matrix. This molecular level mixing process consists of four steps as shown in Figure 1 [16]. The consolidated CNT/Metal nanocomposite shows homogeneously distributed carbon nanotubes within the matrix.

Figure 1. Schematic diagrams depicting strategies and procedures for the molecular-level mixing process; (a) Functionalization of CNT, (b) reaction between the ions and the functional group on the CNT surface, (c) nucleation and growth of metal particles by reduction or solvent evaporation, and (d) CNT/metal nanocomposite powders in which CNT are homogeneously implanted [16].

2.1 CNTs/metal nanocomposites as structural applications

Figure 2(a) shows that the compressive yield strengths of CNT/Cu nanocomposites are much higher than that of Cu, which is fabricated by the same process. Owing to the reinforcement effect of CNT, 5 vol.% CNT/Cu nanocomposite shows the excellent yield strength of 360 MPa, which is 2.3 times higher than that of Cu. Especially, in the 10 vol.% CNT/Cu, the yield strength is 485 MPa, which is more than 3 times larger than that of Cu. In addition, it was also found that Young's modulus of CNT/Cu nanocomposite increases with increasing the volume fraction of carbon nanotubes as observed in Figure 2(b).

For fabrication of CNT/Al-Cu nanocomposites, The CNT/Cu composite powders and Al powders were mixed into the CNT/Al-Cu composite powders using high energy milling [17]. ATCNT and PCNT mean "acid treated CNT" and "PVA coated CNT". The yield strengths of the ATCNT and PCNT/Al-Cu composites with 4 vol.% of CNTs are both 3.8 times higher than the value for the unreinforced Al-Cu matrix (376 and 384 MPa compared to 110 MPa); ultimate tensile strengths are 494 and 470 MPa, which are two times higher than the value of the unreinforced Al-Cu matrix, 237 MPa. For the PCNT/Al-Cu composites, the elastic modulus increases by 30% with 4 vol.% CNT (93 GPa compared to 73 GPa). But, in the case the ATCNT/Al-Cu composites, the increase of the elastic modulus is less than that of the PCNT/Al-Cu composites.

Figure 2. Mechanical properties of carbon nanotube (CNT)/Cu nanocomposites; (a) stress-strain curves of CNT/Cu nanocomposites obtained by compressive test and (b) yield strength and Young's modulus of carbon nanotube (CNT)/Cu nanocomposites [15]

2.2 Graphene/metal nanocomposites as structural applications

Graphene/metal nanocomposites have been also fabricated by molecular level mixing process [18]. First, GOs and metal ions were homogeneously mixed in deionized water; chemical bonds formed between the functional groups of the GOs and the Cu ions. Before producing RGO/Cu nanocomposite powders, mixtures of GOs and Cu ions were oxidized to GO/CuO nanocomposite powders by NaOH solution to prevent reducing functional groups of the GOs before forming the chemical bonds to Cu ions. RGOs decorated with Metal particles were produced after thermal reduction with H₂. Once metal particles are attached on the RGO, no further agglomeration of individual RGOs are possible. Finally, the powders are sintered and densified by spark plasma sintering.

The SEM images showing the surfaces of etched RGO/Cu nanocomposites prove that the RGOs were homogeneously dispersed in the Cu matrix (Figure 3 b). RGOs were also observed at the fracture surface of the RGO/Cu nanocomposites (Figure 3 c). The tensile properties of the RGO/Cu nanocomposites are shown in Figure 3 d. The tensile strength of the 2.5 vol% RGO/Cu nanocomposite (≈ 335 MPa) was about 30% greater than that of pure Cu (≈ 255 MPa). Elastic modulus and yield strength of the sample increased by $\approx 30\%$ (from 102 to 131 GPa) and by $\approx 80\%$ (from 160 to 284 MPa), respectively. Enhanced mechanical properties of the nanocomposites can be explained by the high load-transfer efficiency of RGO in the Cu matrix. The high load-transfer is possible with strong bonding between Cu and graphene mediated by oxygen. The remaining oxygen of RGO in our nanocomposites can supply the strong bonding sites between RGO and Cu.

Figure 3. a) RGO/Cu nanocomposite powders and Consolidated RGO/Cu nanocomposite. Analysis of RGO/Cu nanocomposites. b) Etched surface. c) Fracture surface. d) Stress-strain curves of RGO/Cu nanocomposite. e) Enhancement effect of various reinforcements in the Cu matrix [18].

2.3 CNT/Co nanocomposites as field emission display applications

The CNT-implanted Co nanocomposite for field emitter is fabricated from CNT/Co nanocomposite powders by a screen printing process and followed by a sintering process [19]. Figure 4 shows the schematic depiction and SEM image of fabrication process and formation mechanism for CNT-implanted Co nanocomposite emitters. The Co nanoparticles are sintered together to form a dense metallic thin film layer. The CNTs are straightened and aligned perpendicular to the substrate during the sintering of screen-printed CNT/Co nanocomposite powders. Besides, the turn-on field and current density with other results are compared. CNT/Co nanocomposite field emitter, fabricated by sintering of CNT/Co nanocomposite powders, shows excellent homogeneous field emission behavior with a low turn-on field of 1.28 V/mm and a high current density of 4.5 mA/cm² at 3 V/mm.

Figure 4. Schematic diagrams and SEM images of fabrication process and formation mechanism for CNT-implanted Co nanocomposite emitters; (a) cross-sectional images of screen-printed CNT/Co powder, (b) sintering of Co nanoparticles, and (c) a CNT-implanted Co nanocomposite [19]

3 CARBON BASED NANOMATERIALS/CERAMIC NANOCOMPOSITES

Carbon based nanomaterials can be also utilized as a promising reinforcement for ceramic matrices in order to overcome the intrinsic brittleness of monolithic ceramics. A number of studies with carbon based nanomaterial reinforced ceramic nanocomposites have been reported [20]. Similarly with CNT/metal or Graphene/metal nanocomposites, the critical issue of carbon based nanomaterial/ceramic nanocomposites is to prohibit agglomeration of the carbon based nanomaterials. Agglomerated CNTs and Graphenes act as a defect which could disturb full sintering of nanocomposites. For example, Kai Wang et al., which is the first result of a graphene reinforced ceramic matrix composite for structural applications [22], they mixed RGO and alumina powders by simple mechanical stirring. Although the sintered nanocomposite shows 53 % increased fracture toughness, the theoretical density of the nanocomposite was only 96%. This result shows that homogeneous dispersion of graphene can enhance the mechanical properties of the ceramic matrix nanocomposite further.

Figure 5 (a) An SEM micrograph of surface of a CNT/amorphous-alumina composite powder (b) Variation of the hardness of CNT/alumina nanocomposite with varying CNT volume fraction [23]

3.1 CNT/ceramic nanocomposites

This molecular level mixing process for ceramic matrix is similar to that of CNT and graphene reinforced metal matrix nanocomposite. In order to obtain the oxide, the calcination process is the only different for metal and ceramic matrix nanocomposite. Our first study of carbon nanomaterial reinforced ceramic matrix nanocomposite by molecular level mixing process was CNT/alumina nanocomposite [23]. $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used as a precursor of alumina. The key strategy is that functional groups on the wall surface of acid-treated CNT and Al ions are mixed homogeneously in an aqueous solution at a molecular level. The morphology of CNT/alumina nanocomposite powders shows, unlike simple mixing process, the CNTs are imbedded in the amorphous alumina powders and homogeneously distributed within the powders as shown in Figure 5 a. The nanocomposite powders further calcined and consolidated by SPS, and they shows enhanced hardness (15% increased) and toughness (31% increased) values by adding 0.6 vol.% of CNTs (Figure 5 b). These results show that the molecular level mixing process which is firstly designed for metal matrices can be utilized to ceramic matrix composites. Later, the process for CNT/alumina nanocomposite using molecular mixing process has been modified with adopting ultrasonic spray pyrolysis (USP) process [24]. By the shorten reaction time, the effect of molecular level mixing process was maximized. Due to homogeneous dispersion of CNTs, they shows low percolation threshold value under 0.55 vol.%. On the addition of 4.84 vol.% of CNTs, fracture toughness of the composite increased 2.5 times.

3.2 Graphene/ceramic nanocomposites

The molecular level mixing process which is established from CNT/alumina nanocomposite has been adopted for a graphene/alumina nanocomposite [25]. In order to use functional groups of graphene, graphene oxide was used as graphene. The key feature of strategy is that both hydroxyl (-OH) and carboxyl (-COOH) groups on the surface of GO and Al ions are mixed at a molecular level. Schematic illustration of fabrication process of graphene reinforced alumina nanocomposite powders are shown in Figure 6 a. The evidences of molecular level between graphene and alumina have been verified by FT-IR which indicates Al-O-C bonding (Figure 6 b). Simultaneous strengthening (21.4% increased at 3 vol.%), hardening (14.2% increased at 3 vol.%), and toughening (150% increased at 2 vol.%) have been discovered in graphene/alumina nanocomposite. Figure 6 c shows a bridge of graphenes in the crack area from the indentation. Bridged graphenes and alumina matrix form the strong bond, the “Graphene Bridge” can maximize the load transfer and the dissipation of the crack propagation energy. Schematic illustration for crack bridging by the graphene is shown in Figure 6 d. The molecular level mixing process can be applied to graphene/ceramic composites, and the fabricated graphene/alumina shows an enhanced toughening efficiency with twice surface area compared to that of CNT.

Figure 6 (a) Schematic design for fabricating graphene/alumina composite by molecular level mixing process (b) FT-IR analysis of graphene/a-alumina (red line) and pure a-alumina powders. (c) SEM image of crack area of composites showing crack bridging and blunting of the composites; (d) schematic image of crack bridging and blunting behavior of graphene in the ceramic matrix. [25]

4 CARBON BASED NANOMATERIALS/POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

The introduction of carbon based nanomaterials has prompted the development of polymer nanocomposites for emerging applications of superior mechanical, thermal, and electrical performance. These nanocomposites exhibit excellent structural performance and multifunctional properties. Here, we briefly introduce the material designs and basic interfacial interactions in the carbon based nanomaterials-polymer nanocomposites. Then, we discuss various fabrication techniques available for effectively incorporating the carbon based nanomaterials components into polymer matrices by utilization of weak and strong interfacial interactions available in functionalized CNTs and graphenes. We discuss mechanical and electrical performances which are controlled by processing conditions and interfacial interactions.

4.1 CNT/polymer nanocomposites for structural applications

CNTs has given rise to the possibility of producing new polymeric materials capable of high mechanical performance. We suggest a new melt blending process using PVA as an interfacial material to disperse CNTs homogeneously and, at the same time, provide interfacial strength [26]. The PVA at the interface between CNTs and PC matrix can provide enhanced strain-to-failure in a load transfer condition. The mechanical properties of PVA-CNT/PC nanocomposites increased with increasing volume fraction of CNTs. Young's modulus of the PVA-CNT/PC nanocomposite increased from 489.1 MPa to 564.3 MPa by increasing the carbon nanotube content from 0 wt% to 5 wt%. Tensile strength of the PVACNT/ PC nanocomposite increased from 63.37 MPa to 66.99 MPa. The elongation of 5 wt% PVA-CNT/PC nanocomposite showed a very high elongation of 81%.

We developed method to reinforce the mechanical properties of CNT fibers by the strategy found in the formation of mussel threads [27]. By the spinning of vertical aligned CNTs with infiltration of mussel-mimetic adhesive, the mechanical properties increase remarkably $\sim 500\%$ of the tensile strength of the CNT fibers. The super-strong CNT fibers had a diameter of 15–20 μm , which is larger than reported CNT fibers with the tensile strength greater than 2 GPa, indicating fewer defects in the approach described here. Thus, the mechanical reinforcement achieved by treatment of the mussel-inspired adhesive suggests a new possibility to enhance mechanical properties of other carbon nanocomposite materials.

4.2 CNT(Graphene)/polymer nanocomposites for organic solar-cell (OSC) applications

By integration of CNTs or graphenes in OSC photoactive layers, CNTs and graphenes can act as electron acceptors and replace the conventional electron acceptors like 6,6-phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM). CNTs and graphenes can also provide exciton dissociation sites and charge pathways in the photoactive layer, and the higher conductivities and mobilities of CNTs and graphenes are greater than those characteristic of conventional electron acceptors. Addition of CNTs below 1 wt% in a P3HT/PCBM BHJ system did not negatively affect nanophase separation and increased the PCE up to 4.4% [62] due to enhancement of carrier mobility [28]. We also reported the use of nitrogen-doped RGO (N-RGO) as an electron-selective transport material for P3HT:PCBM systems, as shown in Figure 7. The PCE of an OSC using N-RGO exhibited a 40% enhancement, from 3.2% to 4.5%, compared to an OSC without N-RGO as shown in Figure 7 [29].

4.3 CNT/polymer nanocomposites for other electrical applications

We fabricated pearl-necklace structured CNT/Ni nanocomposite powders by means of a molecular mixing process as mentioned above for GHz-range electromagnetic wave absorbers [30]. We discovered the dispersion effect, mechanical properties, electrical conductivity, and GHz-range absorption properties of CNT/Ni/epoxy. Due to the effect of the nanoscale homogeneous dispersion of the CNT/Ni nanocomposite powders, the electrical and electromagnetic wave absorption properties are enhanced. The CNT/Ni/Epoxy nanocomposite also showed a maximum of four-fold higher electromagnetic wave absorption behavior by improving the reflection loss and the dielectric loss tangent.

Figure. 7 Schematic of the nitrogen doping process of RGO (a) and the BHJ solar cell using the N-doped graphene/P3HT:PCBM active layer fabricated in this work (b) [29].

5 CONCLUSIONS

This review has summarized recent studies on the carbon based nanomaterials composites by various matrices. In case of inorganic matrices such as metal or ceramic, the critical issues on the fabrication of nanocomposites are the homogeneous dispersion of carbon based nanomaterials and strong interfacial bonding with the matrix. Molecular-level mixing process is a novel process to be a good solution for the critical issues. It is because carbon based nanomaterials nanocomposites, fabricated by the molecular-level mixing process, showed significantly enhanced mechanical properties, wear resistance, and field emission properties. Similarly, in case of polymer matrix composites, design of the appropriate dispersion method or the combination processing techniques and finding proper functionalization of carbon based nanomaterials is critical for reaching the best performance.

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